

Full length article

Probing the micro- and nanoscopic properties of dental materials using infrared spectroscopy: A proof-of-principle study

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ABSTRACT

The preservation of oral health over a person's lifespan is a key factor for a high quality of life. Sustaining oral health requires high-end dental materials with a plethora of attributes such as durability, non-toxicity and ease of application. The combination of different requirements leads to increasing miniaturization and complexity of the material components such as the composite and adhesives, which makes the precise characterization of the material blend challenging. Here, we demonstrate how modern IR spectroscopy and imaging from the micro- to the nanoscale can provide insights on the chemical composition of the different material sections of a dental filling. We show how the recorded IR-images can be used for a fast and non-destructive porosity determination of the studied adhesive. Furthermore, the nanoscale study allows precise assessment of glass cluster structures and distribution within their characteristic organically modified ceramic (ORMOCER) matrix and an assessment of the interface between the composite and adhesive material. For the study we used a Fourier-Transform-IR (FTIR) microscope and a quantum cascade laser-based IR-microscope (QCL-IR) for the microscale analysis and a scattering-type scanning near-field optical microscopy (s-SNOM) for the nanoscale analysis. The paper ends with an in-depth discussion of the strengths and weaknesses of the different imaging methods to give the reader a clear picture for which scientific question the microscopes are best suited for.

Statement of significance

Modern resin-based composites for dental restoration are complex multi-compound materials. In order to improve these high-end materials, it is important to investigate the molecular composition and morphology of the different parts. An emergent method to characterize these materials is infrared spectroscopic imaging, which combines the strength of infrared spectroscopy and an imaging approach known from optical microscopy. In this work, three state of the art methods are compared for investigating a dental filling including FTIR- and quantum cascade laser IR-imaging microscopy for the microscale and scattering-type scanning near-field optical microscopy for the nanoscale.

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1. Introduction

Oral diseases represent a significant public health problem worldwide, placing an enormous burden on the healthcare system [1]. The phase-down of amalgam restorations required by the Mi-

namata Convention [2] has not yet been compensated for by an inexpensive and effective restorative material. Higher in cost but with the benefit of unbeatable aesthetics, resin-based composites are the most popular type of restoration today [3]. Modern light-cured resin-based composites (RBCs) offer a wide variation in the chemical composition of each component, their distribution, interaction, and morphology, allowing fine-tuning toward improved bioactivity [4] and mechanical performance [5], lower shrinkage [6], and improved polishability and esthetics [7]. Most fillings perform well over time, however, fracture and secondary caries are the most common cause of failure in composite fillings, with the incidence of fractures increasing significantly [8,9]. In addition, a number of risk factors for the longevity of a restoration have been identified in a recent review that are either related to the patient, particularly those associated with lifestyle and health choices (e.g. risk of caries, parafunctional habits, number of check-ups per year, socioeconomic status), the dentist (experience and the fact that changing the dentist is often associated with a restoration replacement) and the tooth/restoration condition (such as endodontic treatment, tooth type, and number of restored surfaces) [9]. The same review found no influence of the way a restorative material was cured, e.g. the type of polymerization unit or exposure time on secondary caries formation and thus longevity of a restoration [9].

The clinical longevity of a restoration not only depends on the properties of the restorative material, but also to a large extent on the adhesive system that ensures the bond between tooth and composite. These observations led to special attention being paid to the development of adhesives, which are designed for different application methods (e.g. etch&rinse, self-etch, different number of application steps) and, in addition to the purely mechanical interlocking of older systems, aim to actively enter into a chemical bond with the hard tooth substance. Moreover, the collagen degradation by host-derived proteinases [10] and hydrolysis of the bond [11], are crucial for the longevity of a restoration. The effect of these interactions is often tested indirectly, in macroscopic or microscopic bond strength tests [12], but with little power to elucidate bond mechanisms or aging behavior. Therefore, the search for modern investigation methods that can accurately resolve changes in the micro and nano range is becoming increasingly important.

One of the leading analytical techniques for investigating the chemical composition of materials and their interaction with biological structures is infrared (IR) spectroscopy [13]. This technique provides inherent chemical specificity, because infrared light can probe the characteristic vibrations of the chemical compounds in the sample. Consequently, IR spectroscopy makes it possible to identify the chemical components of multi-material systems based on their characteristic absorption signatures, called molecular fingerprint, in the mid infrared (MIR) region, encompassing wavelengths ranging from 2.5 to 20 μm . In addition, infrared spectroscopy is inherently fast, non-invasive, and non-destructive, since only low energy photons interact with the sample and no time consuming and perturbative labeling with dyes or radionucleotides is required. These advantages have led to the broad adoption of infrared spectroscopy for diverse applications, such as polymer science [14], biochemistry [15], energy research [16] and environmental toxicology [17]. Infrared spectroscopy has also been adopted in the field of dental medicine and material research [18,19] to detect early forms of fluorosis [20] and carious processes [21], to investigate the polymerization kinetics of adhesive polymers [22], and to study novel nanoparticles in dental fillings and their effect on bacterial growth [23]. However, spectroscopic studies on dental materials have, so far, mainly relied on traditional IR measurements carried out on bulk materials with low intensity global IR light sources. In such experiments, the investigated dental

materials are studied in isolation from their dental environment and the interaction of resins or composite materials with the environment cannot be studied in sufficient detail. Moreover, significant sample contamination is expected, when the sample is extracted from the tooth section, obscuring the desired dental material information. Furthermore, these studies lack access to spatially resolved molecular information of the heterogeneous samples commonly found in modern high-tech dental materials, as the acquired bulk spectra only show an averaged spectrum over all molecular compounds in the sample masking spatial chemical heterogeneities of the sample. Finally, global light sources have a low intensity, which makes it difficult to detect trace amounts of molecules that may yield important indications about toxic compounds or material failure processes. These challenges have been addressed through rapid advances in infrared optics. For example, the advent of commercially available MIR-Laser sources [24–26] has drastically improved the signal-to-noise ratio of IR spectra and images. Furthermore, the generation of mercury cadmium telluride (MCT) and microbolometer-based focal plane array detectors in combination with, e.g., reflective Cassegrain objectives as well as refractive objectives for laser-based systems have led to the development of spectral imaging infrared microscopes. These microscopes map heterogeneous chemical information with a spatial resolution down to the micrometer range and already constitute a significant advancement of spatial resolution over classical IR-spectroscopy [27–29]. Still, they cannot resolve spectral information on the nanoscale due to the optical diffraction limit. However, through the combination of powerful laser sources and atomic force microscope (AFM) systems, a fundamentally different kind of infrared imaging and spectroscopy technology was invented, that makes it possible to overcome this limit [30,31]. One such infrared microscope is the scattering scanning near-field optical microscope (s-SNOM). This microscope is based on confined optical fields (the so-called near field) created at the apex of the tip of the AFM (see materials and method section). This near field can image and spectroscopically investigate the infrared response of the sample surface with a resolution of about 20 nm, achieving a subdiffraction resolution two orders of magnitude below the diffraction limit of IR light [32]. This conceptual advance gives access to nanoscale infrared spectroscopic information about the structure and chemistry of materials, which is essential to understand and optimize modern-day high-end materials [33].

Already, FTIR-imaging microscopes and s-SNOMs are starting to be applied to dental material research. For example, a FTIR-microscope was used to map and evaluate the formation of a biomimetic interface between the natural tooth and the adhesive and to evaluate the bonding of adhesive to a caries-affected dentin [34,35]. On the other hand, s-SNOM was used to map chemical heterogeneities of apatite nanocrystals close to tubulin structures in the dentin [36] and AFM-IR a method similar to s-SNOM was used to study mineralization and remineralization processes of human dentin [37].

In the context of the increasing number of studies conducted with IR-imaging technologies in dental material research, it is worthwhile to discuss the different strengths and weaknesses of the techniques. In this work, we provide a detailed comparison and overview of three major state-of-the-art IR imaging methods for the study of dental materials. Specifically, we compare the quality of IR-images and spectra of dental filling materials and adhesives from two different far-field methods (FTIR-microscopy (Fig. 1b)) and laser-based QCL-IR microscopy, (Fig. 1c)) and from a s-SNOM (Fig. 1d), an optical near-field microscope. These three microscopy methods are exemplary for the possibilities of modern-day commercial IR imaging, as they span a wide range of IR sources and optics. Still, it has to be mentioned that there are countless

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the investigated dental sample with two kinds of composite adhesive fillings and the mid-IR microscopy techniques used for the comparative study. (a) Sketch of the tooth cross section with two different fillings, both with the same composite, but one containing a commercial adhesive A and the other an experimental adhesive B. The two zoomed in images next to the tooth cross section show the investigated interface between dentin, adhesive and composite. (b) FTIR microscope with a global IR light source and a liquid nitrogen cooled focal plane array (FPA) detector, which enables IR-imaging and FTIR spectroscopy over a broad wavelength range. (c) QCL-IR-microscope based on a quantum cascade laser (QCL) with a high-resolution uncooled detector directly acquiring wavelength dependent IR images and the corresponding reflectance spectra from each pixel of the reflectance image. (d) Rough sketch of an s-SNOM with an atomic force microscopy (AFM) tip raster scanning the tooth surface, operated in tapping mode. The AFM tip is illuminated by a MIR laser source focused on the tip apex and the backscattered light is detected and processed. This enables correlative measurement of AFM-data and IR-images and allows for the acquisition of near-field FTIR spectra of the tooth surface with a resolution of 20 nm, limited only by the tip radius.

other technologies in the field of IR-spectroscopy such as AFM-IR [38] or optical photothermal infrared spectroscopy [39] and this study can only evaluate a part of this technological landscape. In this comparative study, all measurements were performed on the same dental sample with two similar class I cavities prepared in a human third molar and restored with a low shrinkage bulk-fill resin-based composite bonded with two different adhesives (s. Fig. 1a and S1 and materials and methods for further pictures and details of the dental fillings). We choose the specific low-shrinkage composite (see Materials and Methods) to focus on the specific chemical interaction and to not have any damage effects from shrinkages on the bond. Furthermore, the interesting Si-O-Si bond characteristics present in both the ormocer matrix and the fillers have been a compelling target for nanoscale IR-microscopy study.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of dental samples

A freshly extracted human third molar, preserved in a 0.4 % sodium azide solution at a temperature of 4 °C, was selected and cleaned from adherent tissue and debris. The tooth was collected according to the routine at the dental clinic, which involves a network of dentists who collect teeth for research purposes after obtaining their patients' consent to do so and with approval of the ethics committee (No. 19-418KB). Two geometrically similar Class I cavities, 3.5 mm x 3.5 mm x 3.5 mm, encompassing both enamel and dentin areas, were prepared in the mesial and distal aspects of the tooth, using a dental bur. One of the two Class I cavities was then treated with a mild two-step, self-

etching commercial adhesive, which will from now on just be referred to as the adhesive A (Clearfill SE BOND 2, Kuraray Co. Ltd., Kurashiki, Japan) consisting of a self-etching primer and a light-curing bonding agent. The primer was applied to the cavity surfaces with a disposable microbrush and left for 20 s, followed by air drying for 5 s. The adhesive was then applied while using a gentle stream of air to create an even and thin layer of adhesive. The adhesive surface was then light-cured for 20 s using an LED light-curing unit (LCU) (Bluephase Style, Ivoclar-Vivadent, Shaan, Lichtenstein). Finally, the cavity was filled in one increment with a low-shrinkage resin-based bulk-fill composite, which will be referred to as composite (Ormocer, Admira Fusion X-tra, Voco GmbH, Cuxhaven, Germany), and which was light-cured for 20 s with the LCU described above. The second Class I cavity was bonded with an experimental one-step self-etch adhesive, from now on referred to as the adhesive B. The adhesive was applied into the cavity for 20 s with a disposable microbrush and air dried for 5 s. The light curing of the adhesive and the restoration with the resin composite were similar to the above. Details of the chemical composition of the adhesive A and B have been described in detail elsewhere [40]. Briefly, the commercially available adhesive consists of an acidic primer based on 10-methacryloyloxydecyl dihydrogen phosphate (MDP) and an adhesive encompassing MDP in addition to 2-hydroxyethylmethacrylate (HEMA) and dimethacrylate. There is no explicit reference to the presence of inorganic fillers in the commercial material. In contrast, the organic matrix of the experimental adhesives was a mixture of monomers, in which an experimental bisphenol A-glycidyl methacrylate (bis-GMA) monomer was used as a base monomer and triethylene glycol dimethacrylate (TEGDMA) and HEMA were used as dilution monomers. Polyacrylic acid (PAA) was added to create an acidic pH, while the inorganic filler was 7% per weight and consisted of a mixture of 6.8% zircon-hydroxyapatite and 0.2% graphene oxide – zircon oxide particles. The composite material is denominated as Ormocer (organically modified ceramic) and consists of large monomers of modified urethane dimethacrylates (UDMA) [41] with few crosslinks [42] aiming to reduce polymerization shrinkage. Therefore inorganic Si-O-Si networks based on polysiloxanes were produced using a sol-gel process and then cross-linked with polyfunctional urethane and thioether (meth) acrylate [43]. The restored tooth was stored in distilled water at a temperature of 37°C for 24 h. The tooth and implicitly the restored cavities were subsequently cut in half, parallel to the long axis of the teeth and in mesial-distal direction, using a water-cooled, low speed diamond saw (Isomet, Buehler, Lake Bluff, IL, USA). The specimen, exposing the interface between tooth structure, adhesive and composite, was wet finished with a series of silicon carbide abrasive papers (1200 grit, 1500 grit, 2000 grit, 2400 grit, LECO, St. Joseph, MI, USA) and then polished with diamond spray (6 μm , 3 μm , 1 μm ; DP-Spray, Struers GmbH, Puch, Austria) and textile polishing cloths (DP-Pan 200 mm, Struers GmbH). The sample was cleaned ultrasonically (RK 31, Badelin Electronic, Berlin, Germany) for 5 min after each polishing step (see Fig. S1 for a picture of the sample). The tooth sample was kept in distilled water until measurement to avoid dehydration and associated artifacts (microcracks, shrinkage). Before the measurements, the sample was placed in a desiccator with silica gel and evacuated to evaporate any remaining water, which could interfere with the measurements. The drying process was performed gently over several hours and no drying artefacts as such as microcracks could be observed in any of the microscopes.

2.2. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) imaging microscopy

The commercially available FTIR microscope setup used for this study is shown in Fig. 1b. It consists of a FTIR spectrometer (Vertex 80v, Bruker optics, Ettlingen, Germany) which is cou-

pled to an IR microscope (Hyperion 3000, Bruker optics, Ettlingen, Germany). The light source is a global MIR light source with a broad wavenumber range. The light is focused onto the sample by the Cassegrain objective and then transferred to the liquid nitrogen cooled focal plane array (FPA) detector, which operates best in the recommended wavenumber range from 900 cm^{-1} to 4500 cm^{-1} . The microscope records a separate FTIR spectrum at each pixel of the detector. In total, the FPA combines 4096 simultaneous recorded FTIR spectra measurements into a hyperspectral data cube of 64 \times 64 pixels covering a FOV of 170 \times 170 μm^2 . Each pixel represents an area of 2.7 μm^2 on the sample, but the lateral resolution is further reduced due to the diffraction limit and the applied 2 \times 2 binning (i.e. four pixels are averaged to one larger pixel). This size of the FOV is not sufficient to map the entire tooth filling. To obtain a larger FOV, 3 \times 3 and 4 \times 4 images were stitched together, resulting in a total FOV of 510 \times 510 μm^2 and 680 \times 680 μm^2 respectively. All spectra were recorded at a spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Additionally, to the binning, an averaging of 256 scans was applied to improve signal-to-noise. It took around three hours to record an image of the dental fillings using the settings described above. To reduce the influence of atmospheric noise on the measurements, the sample is placed in an acrylic glass box (Bruker optics, Germany) purged with nitrogen. Background reference measurements were performed on a mirror coated with gold (Bruker optics, Germany) before each measurement with the same settings.

2.3. Quantum cascade laser-based infrared (QCL-IR) microscope

The second technique used for this study is QCL-IR microscopy (Fig. 1c). In contrast to the FTIR microscope, the light source is an external cavity quantum cascade laser (EC-QCL) (DRS Daylight Solutions Inc., San Diego, USA) with four different collinear lasers of a wavenumber range from 950 to 1800 cm^{-1} . The monochromatic light is focused by a 12 \times 0.7 NA objective onto the sample and the reflected light is collected. The signal of the reflected light is recorded via an uncooled FPA-detector with 480 \times 480 pixels [28]. The spatially resolved hyperspectral data cube of the reflectance spectra is attained by rapidly tuning the EC-QCL through the whole wavenumber range and recording the reflectance signal at each pixel simultaneously. The whole hyperspectral data cube (230.400 spectra @ 2 cm^{-1} step size) is recorded in about 1 min acquisition time. In this study, the high magnification objective with a field of view of 655 \times 655 μm^2 and a resolution of down to 1.365 μm / per pixel was used for all the recorded images and spectra. The atmospheric noise is reduced by purging the sample chamber with N_2 . Finally, prior to the measurement, reference spectra were taken on a clean gold surface to eliminate any instrumental or atmospheric contributions to the spectral response of the sample.

2.4. Algorithmic porosity determination

In this study, the image processing for the porosity evaluation is conducted with the Hoshen-Kopelman-Algorithm [44], which has already been applied for porosity determination [45]. In this study, the algorithm converts regions with different reflectance into clusters with an index of a size of 5 \times 5 pixels. The clusters are determined by the difference of the reflectance between neighboring pixels. Two neighboring pixels belong to the same cluster if the difference of their reflectance is smaller than a minimum threshold value a . The whole algorithmic process is schematically illustrated in Fig. S2 of the supporting information for a better understanding of the clustering process. The threshold values were chosen such that the pores respectively the area of the adhesives can be easily identified by the algorithm. As the reflectance values vary significantly between the different materials and samples and wavenum-

bers the same threshold a could not be used between different samples and wavenumbers. However, to ensure the comparability of the porosity between the different samples a relative threshold a_{rel} was defined as the average reflectance of the adhesive area of the sample minus the average reflectance of the pores area of the sample divided by the defined threshold value a . This value a_{rel} was kept constant for both the adhesive A and B.

The relative threshold for the adhesive area detection at 1000 cm^{-1} is 2.39 and the relative threshold for the pore detection is 3.6.

2.5. Scattering-type scanning near field optical microscopy

The last microscope used in this comparative study is a commercially available scattering scanning near-field optical microscope (neaSCOPE from attocube systems, Haar, Germany). Its basic working principle is illustrated in Fig. 1d. The device is based on an AFM platform operating in tapping mode, which records a map of the sample topography with a resolution of the AFM tip's apex of about 40 nm in this study. Additionally, the AFM tip is illuminated with an IR laser (E_{in}), which leads to a confined near-field at the apex of the tip, allowing to record surface-sensitive nanoscale optical maps. This strongly confined field is the key for achieving a resolution two orders of magnitude lower than the diffraction limit of IR-light. Due to the interaction between the tip's near-field and the sample surface, the light backscattered from the tip with the electric field E_{scat} is modified depending on the material's dielectric properties. The backscattered light is collected and detected with a liquid nitrogen cooled MCT-detector and contains the characteristic IR-response of the sample below the tip's apex [31,46]. As a mechanism to separate the background signal from the signal of the tip, the detected signal is demodulated with respect to the tip oscillation [31,47]. In our experiments, the second harmonics of the demodulated optical amplitude (s_n) and the phase (ϕ_n) with ($n = 2$) is used in order to achieve a compromise between background suppression and a high signal to noise ratio. In the following the specific imaging and spectroscopy modes of the s-SNOM are explained.

Nano-FTIR. The investigation of the sample's infrared response over a broad wavelength range is possible with the so-called nano-FTIR spectroscopy mode, which is based on an asymmetric Michelson interferometer. In the interferometer, the backscattered signal from the tip is combined with a distance modulated reference beam signal before reaching the detector, and an interferogram resulting from the overlapping beams is acquired. The signal is then demodulated to suppress the background signal and Fourier-transformed to obtain the wavenumber dependent optical amplitude (s_n) and phase (ϕ_n) of the sample. The phase of the optical signal is proportional to the respective near-field absorption of the sample A_n which can be calculated with $A_n = s_n \cdot \sin(\phi_n)$ [32]. The nano-FTIR spectra are of sufficient quality to compare them with classic far-field spectra found in literature. For this mode, a tunable broadband MIR-supercontinuum laser source with a quasi-continuous spectral coverage of about 800 cm^{-1} is employed (from Toptica Photonics, Munich, Germany) [24]. In this study, the spectral maximum was tuned to position C at 1333 cm^{-1} .

White light imaging. White-light images are used to image the sample with the broadband IR-laser source. In this imaging mode, the movable reference mirror of the interferometer is put at a specific position such that all spectral components of the reference and backscattered beam interfere constructively. The resulting white light map of the sample displays the demodulated intensity of backscattered light averaged over the whole broadband laser spectrum. This mode is used to image the sample before recording nano-FTIR spectra on specific areas of interest.

Pseudo-Heterodyne Imaging. The pseudo-heterodyne imaging mode is used for attaining IR resonance specific absorption maps of the investigated sample [46]. The images are attained with a monochromatic or narrow band laser source in combination with a pseudo-heterodyne detection scheme. The laser source in this study is a parametric frequency converter system (Alpha-HP, Stuttgart Instruments, Stuttgart, Germany) with a difference-frequency generating system (MIR module, Stuttgart Instruments, Stuttgart, Germany). It allows for flexible tuning of the emission wavelength from $\lambda = 1.4\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ to $\lambda = 20\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. To attain narrow resonance specific maps, a grating monochromator has been used to limit the output radiation to about 10 cm^{-1} . The detection scheme is based on a vibrating but static mirror in the reference arm of the asymmetric Michelson-interferometer [48]. The modulation of the reference arm in combination with the demodulation of the detector signal results in a background free demodulated optical amplitude and phase signal of the narrow wavelength range, thus, making it possible to map the IR-absorption of the sample with nanoscale resolution at a desired wavelength.

3. Results

3.1. Imaging FTIR-spectroscopy for chemical differentiation

Previous FTIR spectroscopic investigations on bulk samples have identified a rich structure of different vibrational peaks originating from the tooth material and the dental fillings and established connections to biological and chemical processes [18,19]. The central advantage of imaging IR spectroscopy in general is that it can map the chemical composition of a sample based on characteristic IR absorption signatures. The main molecular vibrations of the dental samples investigated in this study are illustrated in Fig. 2a and can be correlated with the main molecular components of the dental filling (see materials and methods). One major vibrational absorption band is associated with the C–O–C stretch at around 1150 cm^{-1} originating from the aliphatic ether groups in monomer building blocks of the adhesive. Further important vibrational bands are the C=O stretching of the ester group in the methacrylate groups of the polymer chains [49] around 1715 to 1735 cm^{-1} and the Si–O stretching in the composite [18]. The Si–O stretch vibration creates a strong absorption feature from around 900 cm^{-1} to 1100 cm^{-1} and can be linked to the Si–O bonds in the glass filler particles in the composite as well as the silica nanoparticles and the Si–O bonds in the polymer chains in the ORMOCER matrix [18]. A final important vibration is the C–H stretching mode found around 2900 to 3000 cm^{-1} , originating from the hydrocarbon compounds found, e.g., in the polymers [18]. Importantly, this mode can only be spectroscopically detected by the FTIR-microscope (see materials and methods for details of the microscope), because the other imaging devices compared in this study utilize laser light sources that cover a smaller spectral range. Based on the first three characteristic wavenumbers, the difference in chemical composition of the dental fillings can be mapped with the FTIR-microscope. Fig. 2b and 2c show the recorded reflectance maps for the adhesives A and B, respectively, at wavenumbers of 1000 cm^{-1} , 1150 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} . The small inset on the left shows the rough location of the reflectance maps in context of the tooth cross section and relates to Fig. 1a. The field of view (FOV) of the FTIR-microscope is too small to map the whole area of interest. Therefore, the acquisition and stitching of multiple images is necessary (see materials and methods). The borders of the individual images are denoted by white dotted lines. This specific area of the dental sample was chosen as it represents one of the most complex areas of the restoration with enamel, dentin, the adhesive and restorative composite all being present in one image, which makes it interesting for the study of the complex chemistry of the different materials

Fig. 2. Spectroscopic investigations of dental fillings featuring different adhesives using FTIR imaging spectroscopy. **(a)** Depiction of the relevant molecular resonances with corresponding wavenumbers. These resonances are directly correlated with the materials contained in the composite and adhesive. **(b)** Recorded reflectance images of the experimental adhesive B at 1000 cm^{-1} , 1150 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} with labels for the different parts of the tooth cross section and white crosses and arrows which indicate the areas of the different parts of the dental section. The small inset on the left shows the approximate location of the imaged area in relation to the whole tooth cross section and relates to Fig. 1a. The complete image is composed of 4×4 single images acquired sequentially and stitched together as highlighted through the white dashed lines. The red rhomb and the orange polygon indicate the location where the red and orange FTIR spectra in **(d)** and **(e)** were acquired. The different materials can be best separated at a wavenumber of 1000 cm^{-1} . **(c)** FTIR reflectance images of the commercial adhesive A composed of 3×3 single images at the same wavenumbers as in **(b)**. The green circle shows the location at which the green spectrum in **(e)** was recorded. **(d)** The plotted spectrum of the composite area of the tooth cross section with a clear Si-O stretching vibration. **(e)** Spectra of both the adhesive A and B with strong carbonyl and C-O stretching and C-H stretching vibrations.

with the IR-microscope. At 1000 cm^{-1} , the enamel and the dentin as well as the composite region show the highest reflectance and can be well separated. The contrast can be explained by the correlation between the reflectance and absorption, meaning materials with a strong absorption show a high reflectance close to their absorption peak. Both enamel and dentin are mainly composed of apatite minerals, which contain many phosphate groups having a strong P-O-stretching resonance at around 1000 cm^{-1} (see supplementary information Fig. S3 and S3 for FTIR spectra of enamel and dentin) [19]. Also, the composite has a strong Si-O stretch resonance around 1000 cm^{-1} due to the silica contained in the ORMOCER matrix and filler particles in the composite. The stronger reflectance of the enamel compared to the dentin can be explained by the degree of mineralization and the higher density of apatite crystals in the enamel compared to the dentin of the tooth [50]. In contrast, the adhesive does not have any strong resonance in this spectral region, which explains the comparative lower reflectance. The reflectance values start to invert with the second map at 1150 cm^{-1} , where the composite and the adhesive show a high reflectance because both materials have a significant amount of ether groups with resonances in this spectral position. Finally, in the last map recorded at 1700 cm^{-1} , the adhesive shows the highest reflectance because the adhesive is based on a methacrylate polymer with a high density of ester groups with an IR-resonance in this region. Notably, the enamel and the dentin can only be separated in the first map at 1000 cm^{-1} , which can be explained by their very low reflectance at the other wavenumbers. Because the imaging FTIR microscope records the full IR reflectance spectrum at every pixel of the mapped sample, precise chemical characterization and localization can be performed at any pixel of the image. Three exemplary positions, for which the absorption spectrum have been plotted (see small symbols in Fig. 2b and c for the exact position), have been picked. The absorption was calculated from the recorded reflectance values with the Kramers-Kroning relations [51]. One of the positions is in the composite region and, as expected, the spectrum (Fig. 2d) is dominated by the strong Si-O vibration, at around 1080 cm^{-1} [18]. The two weak side peaks at approximately 1270 cm^{-1} and 780 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the methyl group found in the silicon organic compounds in the ORMOCER matrix of the composite. The peak at 1270 cm^{-1} corresponds to the Si-CH₃ symmetric bending mode and the peak at 780 cm^{-1} to the respective Si-CH₃ rocking mode [32]. The other two investigated positions correspond to the regions of adhesives A and B. Their absorption spectra are very similar and show the typical IR-resonances of a methacrylate-based polymer (Fig. 2e). As already discussed, the peak around 1150 cm^{-1} originates from the C-O-C stretching mode, while the peaks at around 1260 cm^{-1} and 1370 cm^{-1} are a result of different C-O stretching vibrations and CH₃-bending modes from the methacrylate polymer building blocks of the adhesive [18,49,52]. The absorption maximum at 1730 cm^{-1} is caused by the C=O stretching of ester groups [18,49]. Furthermore, the C-H stretching mode at 2900 cm^{-1} and the O-H stretching mode at 3400 cm^{-1} [49] can be clearly identified. Another vibrational band in the FTIR spectra is located at 1550 cm^{-1} , which relates to the aromatic C=C vibrations of the bis-GMA building block and is often used in relation with the aliphatic C=C vibration from the methacrylate located around 1600 cm^{-1} (see Fig. S5 for a close up of the specific area in Fig. 2e) [53]. Importantly, the bis-GMA building block is the only polymer building block with an aromatic structure and it is only contained in the experimental adhesive B. This shows that the FTIR microscope is sensitive enough to distinguish very similar polymers based on unique building blocks. Furthermore, through monitoring the change in the signal intensity ratio of both peaks the degree of polymerization can be evaluated.

The aromatic C=C vibrations stays constant as the aromatic building block does not take part in the polymerization reaction,

whereas the aliphatic C=C vibration of the methacrylate decreases throughout the polymerization process [53]. By monitoring the spatial intensity ratio of these peaks, crucial information about the polymerization degree in certain areas of the adhesive could be obtained through the use of FTIR microscopy in future studies. In general, the reflectance images and the FTIR-spectra from the FTIR-microscope show that it is easily possible to differentiate chemically heterogeneous samples on the microscale and acquire a understanding of the molecular composition of the sample by plotting the spatially resolved FTIR-spectra. This workflow is especially helpful for characterizing samples with an unknown molecular composition on the microscale, due to the ease with which different materials can first be contrasted by mapping them and then be identified in their composition by FTIR spectra.

3.2. QCL-IR microscopy and porosity evaluation

By combining the high power of laser-based light sources and improvements in imaging performance mediated by high-resolution microbolometer detectors and high-NA refractive objectives, additional insights such as porosity evaluation and statistical evaluation of the spectral quality can be obtained from dental samples through QCL-IR microscopy. In contrast to the imaging FTIR approach presented above, the QCL-IR microscope (see materials and methods for details of the microscope) provides a much larger field of view of $650\text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 650\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, circumventing the need to combine multiple reflectance maps taken at different positions and therefore avoiding stitching artefacts. These reflectance maps are plotted from the corresponding hyperspectral data cubes recorded by rapidly tuning the high-brilliance external cavity quantum cascade laser (EC-QCL) source through the whole range from 950 to 1800 cm^{-1} . Noteworthy are improvements in accelerating the measurements by a factor of up to 170 compared to commonly used FTIR microscopes recently reported with a QCL-IR microscope [54]. The reflectance maps at 1000 cm^{-1} of the adhesives A and B (Fig. 3a and b with the inset showing the approximate location of the map in the overall tooth section) is consistent with the reflectance contrast shown at the above FTIR maps. Importantly, the maps in Fig. 3 resolve the dental fillings with a higher resolution compared to the FTIR images. For example, it is possible to identify small regions of inhomogeneous reflectance in the composite and dentin region of the adhesive A sample. In comparison, these inhomogeneities are only hinted at in the FTIR-maps. The areas with different reflectance contrast can be further investigated by plotting the whole absorption spectrum at specific spatial points (indicated by the small rhombs in Fig. 3a and b) and analyzing the chemical composition through identifying the characteristic fingerprints in these spectra (Fig. 3c).

Like in the FTIR spectra for the adhesives A and B, the main vibrations such as the C-O stretching and C=O stretching vibration peak are clearly visible. However, unlike the FTIR-microscope data shown previously, the large amount of high-resolution spectral data available from the acquired reflectance images opens perspectives for the statistical evaluation of the optical response. To demonstrate this capability, we evaluate the standard deviation of all the spectra within a 20×20 -pixel area around the specified points, which is indicated as the semi-transparent area around the averaged spectra shown in Fig. 3c. In general, the standard deviation is low compared to the peak intensity, showing the high quality of the signal-to-noise characteristics of the spectra. Interestingly, certain peaks show a higher standard deviation compared to other peaks, which could indicate a difference in polymer composition in the averaged area and different polymerization outcome of the cured polymers. Additionally, the high-resolution reflectance images from the QCL-IR-microscope allow to rapidly calculate and evaluate the adhesive porosity as another interesting parameter

Fig. 3. QCL-IR microscopy for chemical mapping and quantifying adhesive porosity. **(a)** IR reflectance image at 1000 cm⁻¹ of the experimental adhesive B filling. The red rhomb and the orange polygon indicate the location where the red and orange spectra in **(c)** were recorded. **(b)** Corresponding IR-image for the commercial filling with the green circle indicating the location where the green spectra of the adhesive A shown in **(c)** were acquired. The different materials of the tooth section and assigned to the specific area by the white crosses or white arrows can be easily differentiated based on the recorded reflectance values. **(c)** Absorption spectra obtained from the reflectance spectra on the adhesive B (orange), adhesive A (green) and composite (red) with resonances assigned to functional groups found in the materials. The semitransparent area around the spectra indicated the standard deviation. **(d)** Scheme for calculating the porosity of the commercial adhesives A from reflectance images at 1000 cm⁻¹ and 1710 cm⁻¹. The reflectance image at 1000 cm⁻¹ shows high contrast between the different material components of the tooth filling and is used to extract the area A of the adhesive with a clustering algorithm. The reflectance image at 1710 cm⁻¹ is used to detect the pores in the image, since it shows strong pore contrast and higher spatial resolution. By combining the whole detected pore area with the adhesive area (A), the adhesive area with pores (P) can be extracted. Then, both areas (A) and (P) are used to calculate the porosity of the adhesive. The porosity of the commercial adhesive A is 4 times higher than the porosity of the experimental adhesive B.

in dental material research. Normally, the porosity determination would be performed with microscale computer tomography and would thus require additional equipment and measurement time. The workflow necessary to calculate the porosity of the different adhesives is based on an algorithm and is shown in Fig. 3 d. The algorithm processes two different reflectance images for each sample shown on the left side of the flow chart. The reflectance im-

age at 1000 cm⁻¹ is used to identify the total adhesive area (A) in the recorded image, as the image at this wavenumber shows a strong contrast between the different dental areas. On the other hand, the reflectance images at 1710 cm⁻¹ reveal the precise locations of pores as dark spots contrasted from the whole dental area. The reflectance of the adhesive is very high at this wavelength and therefore inhomogeneities in the area can be easily detected. The

total adhesive area and the total pore area are detected from the reflectance images using the Hoshen-Kopelman-Algorithm [55,56] (see materials and methods and Fig. S2). The algorithm extracts the adhesive area (A) as a cluster of similar reflectance values, as shown in the lower middle image of the flow chart. The cluster of the pores in the adhesive and composite is extracted from the image at 1710 cm^{-1} (upper middle image in Fig. 3d). Importantly, the identified pores from the composite and the adhesive cannot be differentiated by the algorithm at this wavenumber because the contrast between the composite and the adhesive is low. Therefore, it is necessary to combine the adhesive cluster map and the pore map to extract another map of the pores only located in the adhesive (P) without the pores of the composite. The map of the pores in the adhesive is shown by the last map in the data processing flowchart. In the end, the porosity is calculated by dividing the pore area in the adhesive (P) by the total adhesive area (A). Strikingly, we find a significant difference in porosity between the experimental adhesive B (2.5%) and the commercial adhesive A (9.4%). The results are encouraging as the experimental adhesive with 7% inorganic fillers (see materials and methods for exact composition) mixed into the organic matrix showed smooth processing under laboratory conditions, especially as the mixing process of both components is a source for inducing porosity. In general, the porosity can have important implications for the stability of dental fillings and can be used as a design parameter for the development of adhesives.

3.3. Nanoscale spectral characterization of dental materials with s-SNOM

The study of dental material with nanoscale resolution offers an exciting perspective both for material science and dentistry, because modern composites are complex nanotechnological materials [57]. s-SNOM is one of the state-of-the-art infrared super-resolution microscopy techniques with nanoscale resolution. For optical investigation of the sample, the microscope makes use of an optical near-field at the tip of the AFM induced by a mid-IR laser source (see materials and methods for in-depth explanation of the method). The technique was already used to study the dentin tubuli in a section of a tooth and showed that it could identify microscale hydroxyapatite structures [36]. In this study, the microscope is used to image and spectroscopically explore the dental composite and the interface between the composite and the experimental adhesive B, focusing on interesting chemical heterogeneities in these areas. We particularly choose this area because it gives a challenging but also interesting interface as both the composite matrix and the adhesive are methacrylate based and not easily distinguishable. In addition, scans on the composite were performed to study the interface between the filler particles and composite matrix where possible biodegradation processes can take place. The scan is started by positioning the AFM-tip above a location of interest with the help of an optical overview microscope. The optical microscopy image in Fig. 4a shows the tip placement at the interface between the composite (colored in green) and the adhesive B (colored in blue). Because of its technological versatility, the s-SNOM can operate in multiple modes to analyze the dental materials. An overview of the different modes used in this study is shown in Fig. 4. In every optical imaging mode, a correlated topography image is recorded with the AFM like the one shown in Fig. 4b. The topographic data can be used to distinguish between the adhesive (smooth and flat section in the right upper corner) and the composite even after the grinding process of the dental section. In addition, the topography gives information about the quality of the grinding and polishing process of the dental material. Another important function of the topographic information is that it can be correlated with the recorded optical signals to ver-

ify if the signals truly originate from the optical material contrast and are not topographic artefacts. A better differentiation between dissimilar material sections in the dental filling is possible with the parallel recorded optical imaging modes such as white light imaging (see materials and method section). The dark clusters visible in the white light image (Fig. 4c) with a low optical amplitude show the dense glass filler (84.0 wt.% Ba-Al-Si-glass and SiO_2) embedded in the ORMOCER matrix. Additionally, the interface between the adhesive and the composite can be distinguished because the adhesive exhibits a high and a more uniform scattering signal in contrast to the ORMOCER matrix in the composite. Importantly, the white light imaging mode does not convey any specific chemical information, as it is based on the integrated backscattering intensity and thus only shows optical contrast (see materials and methods for more details). In contrast, the pseudo heterodyne imaging works in this case with a 10 cm^{-1} narrow wavelength range and can probe specific chemical resonances. The pseudo heterodyne image at 1080 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4d) shows cluster particle in the composite matrix imaged based on their Si-O stretch resonance. At this wavelength both the ORMOCER matrix and the glass particles show a Si-O resonance. However due to the material density and resonance intensity of the phononic Si-O stretch of the glass particles, the ORMOCER matrix can still be distinguished from the filler material in the image. For attaining chemical information about a certain area after a white light scan is conducted, a nano-FTIR spectrum can be recorded. Based on the white light map, specific points, or lines of points at a particular position of the map can be investigated. An advantage of this operation mode is that an entire FTIR spectrum is obtained as a broadband laser is used. By comparing two nano-FTIR spectra taken at different positions, the glass particle and the ORMOCER matrix (Fig. 4e blue and orange spectrum) can be clearly distinguished, and the material content can be analyzed. The spectrum of the filler particle shows only one broad peak at about 1080 cm^{-1} originating from the strong Si-O-stretching mode. On the other hand, the ORMOCER matrix shows a richer spectrum. The strongest vibrational mode is the Si-O stretching at 1120 cm^{-1} originating from the Si-O stretch in the silicon polymer. The shoulder at around 1080 cm^{-1} coincides exactly with the recorded Si-O resonances measured on the glass particles. Thus, it seems likely that this shoulder originates from nanosized silica inclusions also contained in the ORMOCER matrix, which are too small to be visualized by white light imaging [58]. The peaks around 1250 cm^{-1} and 1730 cm^{-1} are due to the Si- CH_3 and C=O stretching and the carbonyl stretch from the organic part of the ORMOCER matrix respectively. This short overview of different s-SNOM modes based on the investigated dental material shows the broad applicability of this method for visualizing and identifying dental material components. Especially the pseudo heterodyne imaging mode is useful to investigate heterogeneities in dental fillings, as it allows a direct and fast visualization. Through the imaging of the cluster resonance at 1080 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4d) and at the ORMOCER resonance at 1120 cm^{-1} (Fig. 5a), maps of the cluster distribution and cluster size can be easily obtained. These images can be used in the future to study possible aggregation processes or the distribution of clusters for different composite formulations. Another interesting finding of this imaging mode is the possibility to image the intrusion of the adhesive into the composite matrix and the morphology of cluster particles at the interface as shown at Fig. 5b, when imaging the interface at the cluster resonance of 1080 cm^{-1} and at the resonance of the C-O stretch of the adhesive at 1240 cm^{-1} . The optical maps show a clear contrast between the adhesive B (blue) and the composite area (red). The intrusion can be identified through the small blue islands in the composite layer, which is especially visible when imaged at 1240 cm^{-1} [18]. This method could be used to optimize the interfaces between dental materials, as the interface between the

Fig. 4. Different capabilities of a scattering scanning near-field optical microscopy (s-SNOM) for resolving nanoscale dental morphology and chemical composition. **(a)** Overview image of the optical microscope used to place the AFM cantilever in contact with the surface at the composite (green) and experimental adhesive B (blue) boundary. The red circle in the inset indicates the investigated area of the tooth section. **(b)** 3D AFM topography (z height) map of the composite-adhesive interface showing a clear topographic difference between the flat adhesive and the rough composite section. **(c)** White light image plotted from the second demodulated optical amplitude S_2 correlated to the AFM-image shown in (b). The white light image displays a heterogeneous optical response, which makes it easy to distinguish adhesive, composite, and clusters inside the composite. **(d)** Monochromatic absorption images of the composite area at the second demodulation (A_2) at a wavelength of $1080\ \text{cm}^{-1}$. The filler particles and the surrounding ORMOCER can be separated by their optical response. **(e)** Nano-FTIR absorption spectra from the second demodulation recorded on a glass particle (blue) and on the ORMOCER matrix (orange).

materials can be investigated with a high chemical contrast compared to state-of-the-art techniques such as scanning electron microscopy. In turn this information could help to improve binding properties and interface compatibility of dental materials. Another way to study such crucial interfaces is a hyperspectral nano-FTIR linescan. Such a linescan was performed at the interface between a glass particle and the surrounding ORMOCER matrix. As already shown by the spectra in Fig. 4e the two different materials have only slight spectroscopic differences as they have quite similar Si-O bonds and only differ through a polymer peak and a shift of the Si-O resonance position. The white light scan of the region of interest is shown in Fig. 5c.

The arrow added to the white light scan shows the rough positions and direction, at which the linescan was performed. The close up of the area of the linescan is shown in Fig. 5d, whereby the colored dots show all the positions of each recorded nano-FTIR spectra. The linescan consists of 40 single nano-FTIR spectra at steps of 25 nm over a total distance of 1000 nm. In Fig. S6, the nano-FTIR absorption from the second demodulation at a given posi-

tion is plotted against the distance away from the starting position ($x = 0\ \text{nm}$) of the linescan. From the nanoscale spectroscopic mapping, the glass particle (1st region) and the ORMOCER matrix (2nd region) can be clearly separated from each other. The glass particle region ranging from 0 nm to about 650 nm has a strong Si-O stretch resonance at $1080\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ which decreases when the ORMOCER matrix region is probed at about 650 nm as the response of the ORMOCER matrix is much weaker. The contrast in the spectroscopic data of the two regions is even more pronounced when looking at the relative intensity changes of the absorption between the two regions as shown in Fig. 5e. The relative intensity changes show a clear increase in intensity at the frequency of $1730\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ and a stark decrease in intensity of the resonance at $1080\ \text{cm}^{-1}$. This signal increase can be explained through the carbonyl resonance of the beginning composite matrix. These results show that, using a hyperspectral linescan, the chemical nature of interface heterogeneities can be studied with a very high resolution of a few tens of nanometers. These interface studies are particularly interesting for dental materials showing material failures,

Fig. 5. Nanoscale resolved chemical specific mapping of dental fillings and hyperspectral investigation of a cluster-ORMOCER interface (a) Monochromatic absorption images of the second demodulation (A_2) showing the composite at 1120 cm^{-1} and (b) the composite-adhesive interface at 1240 cm^{-1} and 1082 cm^{-1} (right) with red circles in the insets showing the approximate region where the scans were conducted on the overall dental section. The strongly differing infrared absorption of different materials makes it possible to visualize the heterogeneity of the composite filling and adhesive-composite interface. (c) White light image of the composite matrix with several clusters. The arrow shows the position and direction of a $1\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ long spectroscopic line scan. (d) Shows a close up of the overview white light scan with the exact position of each of the nano-FTIR spectra recorded during the line scan. (e) Relative difference nano-FTIR absorption density plot, whereby the relative near-field absorption signal of the second demodulation between wavenumbers of 1000 cm^{-1} to 1800 cm^{-1} is defined as the difference in absorption between the first spectrum (Position $x = 0\text{ nm}$) taken on the middle of the glass particle and the following spectra at position x . In the density plot, two distinct regions can be identified. The first region is defined by a very strong signal around 1080 cm^{-1} , which correlates with the glass particle location. The second region has a weaker absorption signal at 1080 cm^{-1} and correlates with the beginning of the ORMOCER matrix.

as achieving a deeper understanding of the failure process based on chemical anomalies may, in the future, lead to improvements of the materials used.

4. Discussion

Our comparative study shows that multiscale infrared spectroscopy is a powerful method to understand the complex multi-material systems associated with dental fillings. The acquired spectral data sets provide a unique opportunity to directly compare different state-of-the-art IR microscopy techniques on a dental sample and show the advantages and disadvantages of each individual method and clarifies which spectroscopic and imaging questions they are best suited to answer. The FTIR-microscope possesses a broad range of wavenumbers ($700 - 4500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for detector). This ability, which makes it possible to detect most vibrational peaks,

can even be used to identify all C-H and O-H stretching vibrations at higher wavenumbers. These resonances cannot be detected with the QCL-IR microscopes or the s-SNOM, as it is out of the tuning range of the IR lasers used in this study. The whole spectroscopic response of the sample in each pixel of the FOV can be mapped and is obtained in the form of hyperspectral data cubes. However, the low intensity global light source, which is also used in traditional FTIR-spectrometers, leads to a low signal to noise ratio and causes long integration times of around three hours for a high-quality spectroscopic map of the whole dental filling. Furthermore, the FOV of $170 \times 170\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ is too small to map the whole dental filling, which requires stitching together of single maps to visualize the entire area and can lead to stitching artefacts. In addition, the resolution of the FTIR-microscope is relatively low due to the low resolution of the focal plane array (FPA) detector. This makes it difficult to identify the position of the interface between adhe-

sive and composite from the reflectance maps at 1000 cm^{-1} and the pores at 1710 cm^{-1} .

In contrast, laser-based QCL-IR microscopy is ideal for mapping the dental fillings and for advanced image analysis, because it benefits from a better FPA detector and achieves a higher resolution than FTIR-microscope. The FOV is large enough to image the adhesive, part of the dentin/enamel and part of the composite. An additional advantage is the fast acquisition time for the hyperspectral data cube of the dental sample. It takes anywhere from 1 to 15 min, depending on how much data is averaged to achieve precise results. The high-quality reflectance images can then be utilized to rapidly calculate the porosity of adhesives. The example of the algorithmic porosity detection is just one of many possible uses of high-resolution infrared reflectance maps of the tooth sample. We envision that similar to current trends in label-free, automated digital pathology [54], dental material and tissue can soon be rapidly classified and assessed with the help of artificial intelligence trained on many high-resolution images obtained from QCL-IR microscopes. A disadvantage of QCL-IR microscopy is the limited spectral range of the quantum cascade laser from 950 to 1800 cm^{-1} . Important vibrations above 1800 cm^{-1} such as the C-H stretching vibration located around 3000 cm^{-1} or the cyanide stretching vibration located at 2200 cm^{-1} cannot be detected. This makes it more difficult to map and detect certain chemical groups and processes which are connected to these functional groups.

As opposed to far-field microscopes such as the FTIR- and QCL-IR microscope, which are not able to resolve structures below a few micrometers in size, s-SNOM is perfectly suited to investigate the nanostructure of the samples surface and to decipher chemical heterogeneities on the nanoscale essential for modern day high-tech composite materials. Its resolution is in principle only limited by the radius of the tip, which is in the case of this study around 40 nm . Another advantage of the s-SNOM is that it records topographical maps and optical maps simultaneously. This capability comes with the price of a very small scan area of at the most $100 \times 100\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Additionally, as opposed to the maps obtained by the other two microscopes, the optical map is not a full hyperspectral data cube. The map shows either the IR-absorption of the sample at a very narrow wavelength with the pseudo-heterodyne detection mode or an averaged backscattering intensity of the broadband laser spectrum in the white light mapping mode, which does not carry specific chemical information. The acquisition of FTIR spectra is, of course, possible in the nano-FTIR mode, but already a single point spectrum has an acquisition time of about 2 min thus, making it difficult and time-consuming to attain a full well-resolved and high signal to noise spectral data cube of a large scan area. However, by first attaining a white light map of the sample and then investigating optically interesting areas with nano-FTIR point spectra or a hyperspectral linescan, it is possible to attain nanoscale chemical information in several minutes. Finally, the nano-FTIR mode is limited at the moment by the wavelength range of the nano-FTIR laser of 800 cm^{-1} with five different central tuning points ranging from 600 cm^{-1} to 2000 cm^{-1} . This limits the nano-FTIR investigation to a comparatively small range of wavenumbers for a single spectrum. However, if only a single specific resonance is imaged using the pseudo heterodyne imaging mode, it is possible to obtain images of several micrometer sized areas in a few minutes. Similar results to pseudo heterodyne imaging can also be attained by using the AFM-IR imaging technology, which is based on photothermal expansion as opposed to scattering [37]. Furthermore, a similar study has been conducted in which the authors monitor the degree of conversion and the local polymer strain of similar adhesive polymers with synchrotron-based FT-IR wide-angle imaging with spatial oversampling [59]. This IR-imaging and spectroscopy method has the advantage of a wide spectral range from 4000 cm^{-1} to 800 cm^{-1} , a better signal to

noise compared to the classic FTIR microscope systems and high resolution with an effective pixel size of $0.54\text{ }\mu\text{m} \times 0.54\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ at the sample plane over the whole MIR range and a fast acquisition time of 5 min per FOV. This study nicely demonstrates amount of material related information, which can be extracted from hyperspectral maps of dental materials but is limited in applicability to classic material science laboratories as it is based on an advanced synchrotron light source, which is normally not easily accessible for fast material optimization studies. Finally, raman based imaging and spectroscopy methods should also be thought of, when thinking of methods to analyse complex dental material as the interesting results of for example C-F raman spectroscopy show when analyzing the fluorosis of dental samples [60]. This comparison shows that there is no jack of all trades but that, the right imaging solution needs to be chosen and carefully evaluated depending on the required information.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, we conducted a comparative study of three state-of-the-art IR microscopy techniques on the same dental sample. Our results reveal that all the microscopes can visualize the different functional areas on the dental sample based on the recorded IR-images and characterize their chemical content with IR-spectra. The FTIR-microscope is perfectly suited to identify the most relevant molecular components of the adhesive and composite in the dental fillings by their absorption spectra. Furthermore, it can visualize different materials in the dental section. The images from QCL-IR microscopy show a higher resolution and can be used for more sophisticated image processing such as the rapid algorithmic determination of the porosity of the adhesive. A better understanding of the nanostructure can be obtained with s-SNOM, which can visualize the nanostructures found in the composite as well as the interface between the adhesive and the composite. We envision that these tools of spectroscopic IR microscopy will lead to better insights of the micro- and nanostructure of dental materials and, as a result, in materials with lower failure rates, potentially lower cost, better biocompatibility and a more positive patient experience.

Data availability statement

Data will be made available upon reasonable request.

Author contributions

M. Be. and T. G. contributed equally to this work. M. G., A. T. and N. I. conceived the project. D. P., M. M. and N. I. prepared the dental samples and developed the used experimental adhesive. M. Be. performed QCL-IR measurements and developed the pore detection algorithm. M. Ba. conducted the FTIR measurements. T. G. and E. B. performed s-SNOM measurements. M. Be., M. Ba., E. B. and T.G. analysed the data. A. T., F. K., N. I. and S. M. supervised the project. M. Be. and T. G. wrote the manuscript with contributions from all authors.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: M. Godejohann is owner of MG Optical Solutions GmbH, which is selling and technically supporting QCL-IR based microscopes. F. Keilmann is a scientific advisor to attocube systems AG which manufactures the s-SNOM used in this comparative study. T. Gözl obtained financial support for his PhD thesis from attocube systems AG.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.actbio.2023.07.017](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2023.07.017).

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